

**USING THE DIDACTIC VIEWS OF ABU ALI IBN SINO IN THE
FORMATION OF BASIC COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS**

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Due to his great contribution to the development of enlightenment and culture in the East and Europe, «Shaykh-ur-raï» in the east «Head of scientists», in Europe «The king of scientists» One of the famous scholars is Abu Ali ibn Sina, a great thinker of the Middle Ages. Ibn Sina, along with other contemporary encyclopedic scientists, created in the fields of mathematics, astronomy, physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, pharmacology, psychology, physiology, philosophy, philology, education and education, and left a legacy of great world-famous works.

It is known that Ibn Sina, like other thinkers, expressed his views on education in connection with his socio-philosophical views and interpreted them in special treatises. It also classifies subjects. In this, he puts medical sciences in the first place. Philosophy is divided into two groups, i.e. theoretical and practical groups. If the theoretical group guides people to acquire knowledge about the state of existence outside of themselves, the practical part teaches us what we should do in this world, he says.

He includes ethics, economics, and politics in the first group. The second group includes physics, mathematics, metaphysics, all sciences that study the laws of the world.

Abu Ali ibn Sina calls for the acquisition of enlightenment, which is the first criterion for reaching maturity. Because science should serve people and reveal the laws of nature and pass them on to generations. He says that in order to achieve this goal, a person should not be afraid of difficulties. «O brothers! People's heroes are not afraid of trouble. He who refuses to mature is the most cowardly of men»¹

After all, an enlightened person is brave, he is not afraid of death, he works only to know the truth, he continues.

Uneducated people are ignorant, they cannot know the truth, so they are classified as immature people. He emphasizes that scientific ideas should be kept secret from such people.

He emphasizes that knowledge is necessary to know the truth, but not all

¹ Hasanboeva O., Hasanboev J., Hamidov H. Pedagogika tarixi. T.: 2004, 4-bet

knowledge leads to the truth, and a person needs to know logic in order to know the validity of his knowledge. Ibn Sina's teaching on educational methods is also based on the idea that acquiring knowledge should be based on logical thinking, personal observation and experience.²

Ibn Sina noted the need to teach and educate the child in school, he was against educating the child alone at home, saying that children of all people should be brought to school and taught and educated together. The benefit of having a child study as a team at school is expressed as follows:

If the student studies together, he will not get bored, he will be interested in mastering the subject, he will try to keep up with each other, and he will develop a desire to compete. All this helps to improve reading.

In mutual conversation, students tell each other what they have read from books and what they have heard from adults.

When children gather together, they start to respect each other, make friends, help each other in mastering educational materials, and adopt good habits from each other.

While noting the need to teach children at school to acquire knowledge, he emphasizes the need to observe the following aspects in education:

- ❖ *don't immediately book a book when teaching a child;*
- ❖ *imparting knowledge by going from light to heavy in education;*
- ❖ *exercises should be suitable for children's age;*
- ❖ *pay attention to team teaching in school;*
- ❖ *taking into account the inclination, interest and ability of children in education;*
- ❖ *combining training with physical exercises.*³

These requirements are valuable as they correspond to the principles of modern education. He devotes a special section to the above issues in his work "Tadbiri Manzil". In the section "Education and upbringing of a child at school" ("Education and care of a madrasa child"), the process of education and upbringing is revealed. The above principles will help children to get deep and solid knowledge in all aspects, not just lightly.

²Sharifzoda, S.O va boshqalar. Pedagogika tarixi : O'quv qo'llanma /– Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 172 b

³Sharifzoda, S.O.Umumiy pedagogika : Darslik /– Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 512 b

It is the responsible duty of the teacher to give knowledge to the student. According to this, Ibn Sina, while thinking about what a teacher should be, gives such guidelines. These include the following:

- *being strict and serious in dealing with children;*
- *paying attention to how the students learn the given knowledge;*
- *the use of different methods and forms in education;*
- *student's memory, ability to acquire knowledge, knowledge of personal characteristics;*
- *interest in science;*
- *able to distinguish the most important of the given knowledge;*
- *imparting knowledge to students in a way that is comprehensible to them, in accordance with their age and intellectual level;*
- *the scientist says, it is necessary to achieve that each word is at the level of arousing children's emotions.*

According to Ibn Sina's teaching, no matter what methods are used in learning - whether it is verbal expression, explanation of knowledge, different forms of conversation, experiments, the main thing is to create real knowledge in the student, to develop the ability to think independently and logically, and to develop the ability to put the knowledge into practice. was the goal.

In this regard, the scientist's work "Hay ibn Yaqqan" is of great importance in education as it develops people's taste and insight and expands the range of thought. His name also refers to this: "Hay ibn Yaqqan" (Son of the Awake is Alive). Ibn Sinani himself states that this work is about the science of divination. It is said that ibn Sina wrote this work in 1023 in the prison of the Faradjon fortress near Hamadan.

In this work, Ibn Sina narrates that his eyes were opened as a result of his study of knowledge, that reason (Hay ibn Yaqqan) appeared to him, and knowledge showed its beauty to him. He describes him as the bright one who does not know death, who does not grow old, who does not bend his back, and is bright. He notes that he began to study things that were necessary and that he could know, and that he used his mind and learned about various features that would keep him away from evil.

Therefore, "Hay ibn Yaqqan" is of great importance in intellectual education even though it is devoted to the science of logic. In addition, it is not only a literary-philosophical work, but also valuable as an educational work, as it is a tool to get rid of bad vices and realize the importance of science and intelligence in the elimination of bad vices in a person.

Ibn Sina emphasizes that his moral maturity is important for a person's maturity.

Researchers note that he thought about ethics in his philosophical works.

Ibn Sina calls his works on ethics "Practical Wisdom" (Practice of Wisdom). According to the scientist, the science of ethics studies the norms and rules of behavior of people in relation to themselves and others.

Ibn Sina defines the basis of morality with two concepts such as good and evil: Everything that exists in the world tends towards perfection by nature. And the pursuit of perfection itself is essentially good..."

Ibn Sina also analyzes the important moral aspects of human perfection and defines each of them: for example, he considers justice to be the main criterion of spiritual pleasure. According to the scientist, a person acquires justice with contentment, courage, and wisdom, refrains from bad vices, strengthens goodness, and gets real spiritual pleasure. It includes generosity, endurance, humility, love, moderation, intelligence, prudence, determination, loyalty, aspiration, shyness, performance, etc. among the positive moral qualities of a person.

Brings contentment and moderation to a person's emotional strength; Endurance, intelligence to the power of anger, wisdom, prudence to intelligence; Loyalty, shyness, performance, pity, honesty enter into the power of difference.

The scientist considers contentment as one of the emotional qualities and says that if a person refrains from greed, observes moderation, overcomes the manifestations of greed, a person should consciously use his abilities to overcome bad vices.

Ibn Sina gives a definition of each moral character: moderation - not doing things that do not correspond to the necessary food and behavior standards for the body;

Generosity is a human power that helps people in need;

anger - courage to do something; Endurance is the power that a person can withstand the evils that happen to him;

intelligence is the ability to prevent haste in doing something. Intelligence is the power that helps to quickly understand the true meaning of things and even actions; pity, the human power to be kind to people when they are in misfortune and suffering; defines humility as a force that prevents us from engaging in selfish activities.

Ibn Sina points out ignorance, ignorance, cruelty, arrogance, and hatred as defects that hinder human development. He describes ignorance as the opposite

of knowledge, ignorance as the opposite of intelligence, cruelty, arrogance as the opposite of justice, and hatred as the opposite of love.

Ibn Sina also includes the high moral qualities of people living as friends and cooperation. Because everyone, while living in society, with people, strives to live friendly with them.

As long as a person needs contact, he builds a house next to someone else's house in order to be a neighbor, and in order to satisfy his needs, he exchanges production products, and unites with others in order to avoid enemies. This is how people begin to develop a sense of unity, love for others, and common moral principles. He says that a well-mannered and knowledgeable friend plays an important role in the formation of good character in a person. This is how the scientist defines friendship:

- ❖ *friendship that does not leave its friend alone in danger despite all difficulties;*
- ❖ *close friendship with similar interests and ideals;*
- ❖ *friendship aimed at satisfying one's personal interests and needs.* ⁴

Ibn Sina recognizes the first and second kind of friendship as true friendship. The scientist says that true friendship can lead to love. He sheds light on the true essence of love in the work "*Risolai ishq*" both socially and physiologically. It shows that people should be judged not by their external appearance, but by their inner, spiritual world. Everyone has a feeling of love by nature, it is manifested as a natural necessity, but a person can control his feelings, with intelligence and insight, he can distinguish true love from the feeling of lust, the power of passion. Because true love, according to the scientist, imposes a moral and legal duty on a person. This shows that the scientist considered love as a social factor.

Researchers report that ibn Sina also created musical works, but only a part of them has reached us.

One of them is the "Collection of Music Knowledge", which focuses on such issues as the impact of sound on the senses, its pleasantness and unpleasantness, and the emergence of a feeling of pleasure or aversion when hearing a sound. It also shows the importance of music in human life. According

⁴Sharifzoda, S.O. va boshqalar. Umumiy pedagogika : O'quv qo'llanma /– Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 230 b

to the scientist, if a person is relieved by things that are pleasant in nature, then his calmness will disappear and hatred will appear. Ibn Sina also expresses his opinion about the influence of musical sounds on the human soul.

Ibn Sina's works on music are also valuable because they provide very important information about the music science of his time.

Ibn Sina taught that intellectual education is realized as a result of learning various knowledge, while moral education is realized more through practicing good moral qualities, habituation, conversation.

Since a person has the ability to distinguish between emotional and spiritual needs, this ability gradually becomes a characteristic of human character. Ibn Sina said that in the formation of a person, the external environment surrounding him, people play a special role, and this external environment and people affect not only the knowledge of the surrounding world, but also the formation of good or bad aspects in his behavior. That is why it is necessary to be careful in raising children, to keep the child away from bad people and bad environment so that he does not learn bad habits.⁵

In the educational views of Ibn Sina, family and family upbringing issues are given a wide place. Because a person matures first in the family.

The scientist pays great attention to the role and duty of parents in the family. Touching on family relations, he expresses important thoughts about parents' hard work in the family and training their children in professions and trades. In addition to emphasizing the positive effect of work on human behavior and spirit, he glorifies the work of various professions: artisans, farmers, and condemns gamblers and usurers. He correctly interprets that living without work has a negative effect on a person both physically and mentally.

Along with intellectual and moral education, Ibn Sina analyzes the importance of physical education in human development both theoretically and practically.

Until Ibn Sina, there was no comprehensive teaching about the effect of physical education on human development. Ibn Sina was the first to create a scientific and pedagogical system of physical education.

He proved that physical exercises, proper nutrition, sleep, keeping the body clean are important factors in maintaining human health both scientifically and

⁵Sharifzoda, S.O. Xudaynazarov E.M. Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi : Darslik /– Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 310 b

practically.

He demonstrated the scientific and cultural power of the medieval East to the whole world with his knowledge and heritage. He made a great contribution to the development of human culture.

That is why Ibn Sina was recognized as a great figure of world culture, a respected scientist, a great physician, the greatest philosopher, naturalist, humanist, and famous encyclopedist.

Taking into account Ibn Sina's contribution to the development of world science and culture, Jordano Bruno puts Ibn Sina on an equal footing with Aristotle, the great philosopher of ancient Greece, (physician) Golenlar, and A. Dante in his "Divine Comedy" Equals Ptolemy, Euclid, Hippocrates. The German philosopher L. Feyrbach called the scientist a "famous physician and philosopher", while the great Indian statesman J. Nehru mentioned Central Asian scientists in his work "The Discovery of India" and highlighted the name of Ibn Sina: "Among them He respectfully mentions that the most famous (physicians) is Ibn Sina (Avicenna) from Bukhara, who received the name "king of physicians".

Therefore, Ibn Sina's personal activity, his teachings on the study of worldly sciences, his comments on education have a unique place in the development of universal pedagogical thought, and are of great importance in the formation of basic competencies in students.

References:

1. Sharifzoda, S.O. Xudaynazarov E.M. Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi : Darslik /- Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 310 b
2. Sharifzoda, S.O. va boshqalar. Umumiy pedagogika : O'quv qo'llanma /- Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022.
3. Sharifzoda, S.O va boshqalar. Pedagogika tarixi : O'quv qo'llanma /- Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022. - 172 b
4. Hasanboeva O., Hasanboev J., Hamidov H. Pedagogika tarixi. T.: 2004, 4-bet;